

UTH-Olympia@BC8 Track 3: Adapting GPT-4 for Entity Extraction and Normalizing Responses to Detect Key Findings in Dysmorphology Physical Examination Observations

Ekin Soysal^{1,*} and Kirk Roberts¹

¹McWilliams School of Biomedical Informatics, University of Texas Health Science Center at Houston, Houston, TX

*Corresponding author: E-mail: Ekin.Soysal.1@uth.tmc.edu

Abstract

In this paper, we present our approach for the Biocreative VIII Track 3: Genetic Phenotype Extraction from Dysmorphology Physical Examination Entries (genetic conditions in pediatric patients). The aim of this track is to extract and normalize key findings present in dysmorphology physical examinations. We report an automated system relying on OpenAI's most recent large language model (LLM): GPT-4 to retrieve named entities and their spans from observations and normalize retrieved entities to Human Phenotype Ontology (HPO) concepts using dictionary matching algorithms. Our reported systems achieved an F1 score of 0.82 for standard matching in subtask 3a and an F1 score of 0.72 for exact matching in subtask 3b.

Introduction

The Biocreative VIII Track 3: Genetic Phenotype Extraction from Dysmorphology Physical Examination Entries (genetic conditions in pediatric patients) is motivated by the need to systematically extract key medical findings from unstructured data for performing downstream computational analysis. In this shared task, competitors were provided with a dataset of dysmorphology physical examinations that are documented as a series of organ system observations. The goal was to create an automated system, relying on advanced natural language processing (NLP) methods to extract key findings from the given observations and normalize them to concepts in the Human Phenotype Ontology (HPO). Subtask 3a evaluated the performance of detecting the correct HPO concepts in given observations, and subtask 3b evaluated the performance of detecting the character spans for each HPO concept extracted by the system.

To solve this problem, we have decided to utilize OpenAI's (2023) most recent large language model (LLM): GPT-4. There have been previous studies that utilized GPT models to perform named entity recognition (NER) and concept normalization. Chen et al. (2023) studied baseline performances of GPT-3.5 and GPT-4 across NER and other applications in biomedical informatics. Wang et al. (2023) proposed an approach, GPT-NER, in which GPT-3 would extract spans of concepts with high performance by marking the concept with special characters in text. Li and Zhang (2023) compared performance of GPT-NER and other recent LLM-based approaches for NER in biomedical informatics to older approaches such as those that utilize BERT-based models.

Material and Methods

Preprocessing and Dataset Updates

To promote consistency across different observation annotations, we have applied several updates to the original dataset provided by the shared task. Among the occasional human errors, we have two primary reasons to make such updates to the original dataset. Firstly, we aimed to increase consistency for spans annotated for a given concept, which would enhance performance for predicting spans. The first and second rows of Table 1 show one such example. Secondly, we aimed to increase consistency for concepts mapped to a given named entity. Such errors when annotating may arise from multiple concepts existing in HPO that are close matches for a single named entity. Resolution of such inconsistencies also reduces conflicts for our dictionary matching approaches, which will be discussed in the following sections. The third and fourth rows of Table 1 show such an example. In the end, a total of 48 concept annotations out of 2770 in the training dataset and a total of 13 concept annotations out of 734 in the validation dataset were updated. Both types of inconsistencies were detected using automatic methods and were later manually reviewed and updated based on similar annotations in the rest of the dataset and annotation guidelines.

To maximize performance for the task of finding abnormal findings, we have also removed 329 concept annotations from the training dataset and 78 concept annotations from the validation dataset that recorded normal findings. Despite their presence in the dataset, the normal findings are not a part of the evaluation process in this shared task, and therefore it is best not to provide undesired information to the classifiers during training.

Table 1. Dataset Inconsistency Examples.

Inconsistency Type	Observation ID	Dataset	Exact Annotated Observation	HPO ID
Span	8bb2b415c3263e47b2303bf45efec958	Training	EYES: Prominent [infraorbital creases]	HP:0100876
Span	001d6c29f4e6ab6d37e2a4b0b84db25c	Validation	EYES: [Prominent infraorbital creases].	HP:0100876
HPO Concept	5d1c983da5c12cd593edc75ee9548f76	Training	NECK: [Excess nuchal skin].	HP:0005989
HPO Concept	a23e72ed8d70c59e91ad638f4329ff14	Training	NECK: [excess nuchal skin] and	HP:0000474

Extracting Named Entities with GPT-4

We used OpenAI’s ChatCompletion API with the GPT-4 model to extract named HPO entities from given observations. We have asked GPT-4 to extract abnormal key findings according to the representation in Table 2. In the system prompt, the mention of ‘abnormal’ reinforces exclusion of normal findings, and the mention ‘HPO’ encourages focus on phenotype entities in the generated assistant response.

Table 2. Prompt Template Representation.

System Message	Extract Human Phenotype Ontology (HPO) concepts for abnormal key findings from the given text. Return HPO term and marked original text with square brackets surrounding the words associated with the HPO term.
User Message	NECK: Excess nuchal skin.
Assistant Message	Redundant neck skin NECK: [Excess nuchal skin].

We made one request to GPT-4 per observation, aiming to extract all entities in the observation. In each request, we asked for two items, separated by a ‘|’ character, per entity found. The first item is the entity term. The second item is the modified version of the observation text (the same text we sent to GPT-4) where words associated with that entity were marked with square brackets.

For each entity, we used the first item, extracted entity term, for normalization purposes, which will be discussed later. We used the second item, marked observation text, for span

extraction for the corresponding entity, and also for normalization purposes. The locations of square brackets allow for identification of the character offsets for each entity.

Requesting a text marked with squared brackets allows us to extract entity spans, continuous or discontinuous, significantly more accurately compared to directly retrieving span character offsets using GPT-4. Based on our experiments, attempting to directly request character offsets will return inaccurate results most of the time, due to GPT-4 not being proficient in the task of identifying character offsets in general.

However, there are also shortcomings in asking GPT-4 to mark the text. Occasionally, GPT-4 will return a slightly different observation text than the one provided in the request. These differences include typo fixes performed by GPT-4 and differences in the usage of special characters such as '+'. We were not able to correct this behavior reliably with prompt engineering and providing examples, therefore, a small percentage of our errors are caused by this issue. On occasions where an extracted concept had span offsets that would be out-of-bounds for the original observation text, the extracted concept was discarded.

Few-Shot Learning

To better convey our intent to GPT-4, we added examples on each request according to the few-shot learning technique. Since the GPT-4 model we used allowed for 8k tokens per request, we used 25 examples per request. These examples were inserted between the system message and the final user message (the actual observation text we wanted GPT-4 to extract named entities from). Each example consisted of a user message, which included an observation text similar to the final user message mentioned previously, and an assistant message, which included the two items mentioned in the previous section for each entity present in the observation text according to our dataset.

For each request, the list of few-shot examples was generated using three steps. In the first step, we selected observations from the training set that were most similar to the final observation text of the request and included at least one concept annotation. We used spaCy document similarity for this approach, which performs a cosine similarity using an average of word vectors (Honnibal & Montani, 2017). 15 out of 25 examples were selected using this method.

For the second step, we append a manually selected list of 5 examples per body part to include 'tricky' examples. These examples were mostly aimed to guide GPT-4 through task requirements that were not always followed when solely described in the system prompt. Such requirements included the ability to determine span offsets correctly for examples that required tagging the header body part located in each observation, or for excluding modifiers such as 'slightly' or 'mild', which almost always conflicted with the annotation guidelines.

In the third step, we add the 5 most similar negative examples from the training set to the final observation text of the request to our examples list. A negative example refers to an observation that does not include any key findings, and therefore has no entities to extract. This ensures that GPT-4 understands it has the option to extract no entities if applicable and shows it how to return an empty response.

Concept Normalization of Entities Extracted by GPT-4

Among our submissions, we have used two different approaches that took GPT-4 outputs as input and returned a list of HPO concepts and offsets from them. For both approaches, we have built a dictionary of terms that map to HPO IDs. The dictionary included preferred terms and synonyms of all HPO concepts labeled observable by the shared task. Additionally, the terms observed in the

observation texts within the training dataset were added to the dictionary as well. Each term in the dictionary was stemmed to better facilitate exact matches.

For our first matching algorithm, we have disregarded the named entity extracted by GPT-4 in the first item and only relied on the named entity found in the marked observation text in the second item. We have searched this named entity in our dictionary after stemming, and recorded the matching concept if there was any.

For our second matching algorithm, we have replicated the exact steps we take in the first algorithm. However, if we found no matching concepts after using the named entity from the marked observation text, then we used the named entity extracted by GPT-4 in the first item to attempt another dictionary match. If we found a match this way after failing to find a match with the named entity from marked observation text, we recorded the matching concept.

Results and Discussion

In the evaluation step of the Biocreative VIII Track 3: Genetic Phenotype Extraction from Dysmorphology Physical Examination Entries shared task, we have received a maximum F1 score of 0.82 for subtask 3a, and a maximum F1 score of 0.72 for subtask 3b after evaluation on the test set. We have presented Table 3 below, listing all scores available. In Table 3, Algorithm 1 refers to using GPT-4 with few-shot learning for named entity extraction and using only the named entities from marked observation text to normalize named entities to HPO concepts. Algorithm 2 refers to using GPT-4 with few-shot learning for named entity extraction and using both named entities from marked observation text and named entities determined by GPT-4 to normalize named entities to HPO concepts.

Overall, Algorithm 2 performed better, achieving higher F1 scores in all categories. However, it is worth noting that Algorithm 1 consistently achieves significantly high Precision values across all categories.

Table 3: Performance on Test Set.

Approach	Normalization Only			Overlapping Extraction and Normalization			Strict Extraction and Normalization		
	Precision	Recall	F1 Score	Precision	Recall	F1 Score	Precision	Recall	F1 Score
Algorithm 1	0.9363	0.5604	0.7011	0.9361	0.5588	0.6999	0.9313	0.5175	0.6653
Algorithm 2	0.8417	0.7989	0.8197	0.8409	0.7941	0.8168	0.8104	0.6423	0.7166

Over the course of development towards our final algorithms, we have observed that similarity-based few-shot learning supplement to the prompt increase the performance significantly. Before applying few-shot learning techniques, we had attempted to have GPT-4 to adopt distinct behaviors required by this task via system prompts. Such behaviors included consistent exclusion of modifiers, particular styles of inclusions of body locations in spans, and returning correctly formatted ‘No entities found’ message when appropriate. However, we were not able to accomplish consistent success in such cases with this method alone. We attempted to ask GPT-4 to give suggestions on how to modify system prompts to guarantee consistency, but it found our prompts appropriate and could not suggest any solutions to improve the performance. In the end, switching to few-shot learning in which such behaviors were shown via examples worked much better, and enforced such behaviors consistently enough.

References

1. OpenAI. (2023). GPT-4 Technical Report. *arXiv*. <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2303.08774>
2. Chen, Q., Du, J., Hu, Y., Keloth, V. K., Peng, X., Raja, K., Zhang, R., Lu, Z., & Xu, H. (2023). Large language models in biomedical natural language processing: Benchmarks, baselines, and recommendations. *arXiv*. <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2305.16326>
3. Wang, S., Sun, X., Li, X., Ouyang, R., Wu, F., Zhang, T., Li, J., & Wang, G. (2023). GPT-NER: Named entity recognition via large language models. *arXiv*. <https://arxiv.org/abs/2304.10428v4>
4. Li, M., & Zhang, R. (2023). How far is language model from 100% few-shot named entity recognition in medical domain. *arXiv*. <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2307.00186>
5. Honnibal, M., & Montani, I. (2017). spaCy 2: Natural language understanding with Bloom embeddings, convolutional neural networks and incremental parsing. <https://sentometrics-research.com/publication/72/>